

Amperometric Titrations of Uranyl Nitrate with Alkali Arsenites

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The reaction between UO_2^{2+} and different alkali arsenite anions ($\text{As}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$, As_2O_3^- and $\text{As}_2\text{O}_3^{0-}$) has been investigated by means of amperometric titrations at $E_{d.e.} = -1.0$ volt (vs. S.C.E.) The well defined breaks obtained from titration curves evidenced the formation of uranyl ortho— ($3\text{UO}_2\text{O}.\text{As}_2\text{O}_3$) pyro—($2\text{UO}_2\text{O}.\text{As}_2\text{O}_3$) and meta ($\text{UO}_2\text{O}.\text{As}_2\text{O}_3$) arsenites in the pH ranges 7.0–9.9, 6.0–7.5 and 5.0–6.8 respectively. The results are accurate and reproducible; the precipitation of these compounds has been found to be almost quantitative and the titrations can be suitably employed for the amperometric estimation of UO_2^{2+} ions in solutions by the use of arsenite.

There is no reference in the literature regarding the amperometric titrations of uranyl salts with different alkali arsenites at different pH levels and the composition of uranyl arsenites thus formed. The present investigation has, therefore, been initiated.

Merck's guaranteed extra pure reagents—uranyl nitrate, sodium hydroxide, thymol and sodium perchlorate were used. Air-free conductivity water was used for the preparation of solutions. Sodium pyro-arsenite and sodium ortho-arsenite solutions were prepared by adding requisite amounts of NaOH in boiling solution of sodium meta-arsenite.

A manual polarograph with a scalamp galvanometer as a current recorder was used in these investigations. A capillary having the following characteristics : $m = 2.416$ mg/sec., $t = 3.58$ sec., and $m^{\frac{2}{3}}t^{\frac{1}{3}} = 2.226$ $\text{mg}^{\frac{2}{3}}\text{sec}^{-\frac{1}{3}}$ was used in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell by a low resistance salt bridge. Twenty ml of titre solution was taken in the cell each time and hydrogen was used for deaeration and stirring of solutions. Employing different concentrations of reagents—uranyl nitrate and alkali arsenites, a series of amperometric titrations were carried out in the presence of 0.1 M NaClO_4 and 0.01% thymol both by direct and reverse methods using each of the reagent alternately as titrant, which was added by means of a microburette of the accuracy of 0.01 ml. In all the amperometric titrations a potential of -1.0 volt (vs. S. C. E.) was applied to the electrodes, which is the limiting current plateau potential of the second step of polarogram produced by uranyl ions. The concentrations employed and the observed end points have been summarised in table I. Two figures illustrating direct (fig. 1) and reverse (fig. 2) titration curves of different arsenites have been given for the sake of brevity.

TABLE I
Summary of results of amperometric titrations.

Molarity of solutions.		Equivalence points		Formula supported.
		Calculated.	Observed.	
<i>Ortho-arsenite titrations.</i>				
$\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	$3\text{Na}_2\text{O}.\text{As}_2\text{O}_3$	Direct titrations	Fig. 1, curve I.	$3\text{UO}_2\text{O}.\text{As}_2\text{O}_3$.
M/20	M/500	2.4	2.35	
M/30	M/550	3.27	3.25	
M/40	M/800	3.0	3.0	
M/50	M/900	3.33	3.3	
		Reverse titrations	Fig. 2, curve I.	
M/300	M/100	2.22	2.25	
M/400	M/125	2.08	2.1	
M/500	M/150	2.0	2.0	
M/750	M/200	1.78	1.8	
<i>Pyro-arsenite titrations</i>				
$\text{UO}_3(\text{NO}_3)_2$	$2\text{Na}_2\text{O}.\text{As}_2\text{O}_3$	Direct titrations.	Fig. 1, curve II.	Formula supported $2\text{UO}_3\text{O}.\text{As}_2\text{O}_3$.
M/20	M/200	4.0	3.95	
M/30	M/450	2.66	2.65	
M/40	M/500	3.2	3.2	
M/50	M/700	2.86	2.85	
		Reverse titrations,	Fig. 2, curve II	
M/250	M/50	2.0	2.0	
M/350	M/75	2.15	2.2	
M/450	M/100	2.2	2.25	
M/500	M/125	2.5	2.55	
<i>Meta-arsenite titrations.</i>				
$\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	$\text{Na}_2\text{O}.\text{As}_2\text{O}_3$	Direct titrations.	Fig. 1, curve III	$\text{UO}_2\text{O}.\text{As}_2\text{O}_3$.
M/20	M/250	1.6	1.6	
M/30	M/300	2.0	1.95	
M/40	M/350	2.29	2.25	
M/75	M/500	3.0	2.95	
		Reverse titrations,	Fig. 2, curve III	
M/200	M/25	2.5	2.55	
M/500	M/50	2.0	2.05	
M/750	M/70	1.86	1.90	
M/900	M/100	2.2	2.2	

DISCUSSION

Ortho-arsenite titrations :—The pH of uranyl nitrate and sodium ortho-arsenite solutions as measured on a glass electrode was found to be in the vicinity of 4.0 and 12.0 respectively. Using different concentrations of these reagents, a series of amperometric titrations were performed in the presence 0.1 M NaClO_4 and 0.01% thymol at $E_{d.e.} = -1.0$ volt (vs. S. C. E.) at which the uranyl ions yield a well defined reduction wave while arsenite ions do not produce any diffusion current. In direct titrations (fig. 1, curve I), i.e., when ortho-arsenite solution was used as titre, the observed current of the magnitude of a few microamperes remained almost unchanged

on the addition of uranyl nitrate solution till the end point is reached, after which the current due to the uranyl ions increases linearly with the addition of the latter. In

FIG. 1

Fig. 1. Direct amperometric titrations between uranyl nitrate and sodium arsenites (ortho-curve ; I pyro-, curve II ; meta-, curve III).

Curve I—ml. of M/20 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ added to 20 ml. of M/500 $3Na_2O.As_2O_5$.

Curve II—ml. of M/20 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ added to 20 ml. of M/200 $2Na_2O.As_2O_5$.

Curve III—ml. of M/20 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ added to 20 ml. of M/250 $Na_2O.As_2O_5$.

FIG. 2

Fig. 2. Reverse amperometric titrations between uranyl nitrate and sodium arsenites (ortho—curve I ; pyro-, curve II ; meta-, curve III).

Curve I—ml. of M/100 $3Na_2O.As_2O_5$ added to 20 ml. of M/300 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$.

Curve II—ml. of M/50 $2Na_2O.As_2O_5$ added to 20 ml. of M/350 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$.

Curve III—ml. of M/25 $Na_2O.As_2O_5$ added to 20 ml. of M/200 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$.

the case of inverse titrations (fig. 2, curve I) when ortho-arsenite solution was added from microburette to uranyl nitrate solution, the reverse phenomena was observed. Both the direct and reverse amperometric titrations curves provide well defined breaks at the point where the molecular ratio of UO_2^{2+} and $\text{As}_2\text{O}_3^{6-}$ is as 3 : 1 and indicate the formation of lemon yellow uranyl ortho-arsenite of the composition $3 \text{UO}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{As}_2\text{O}_3$ at pH range 7.0—9.9 according to the following equations :

Pyro-arsenite titrations : The solution of alkali pyro-arsenite was prepared as described earlier and its pH was found to be nearly 11.0. Several amperometric titrations were performed with uranyl nitrate under identical conditions. The shape and nature of the titration curves have been found to be similar to that of ortho-arsenite titrations. Both direct and reverse titrations yield well defined breaks at the end point suggesting the quantitative precipitation of uranyl pyro-arsenite (pH = 6.0—7.5). The reactions can be represented as follows :

Meta-arsenite titrations : The pH of sodium meta-arsenite solution was found to be in the neighbourhood of 9.80. Figs. 1-2, curve III, illustrate the changes occurring in current values during the addition of uranyl nitrate to sodium meta-arsenite and vice-versa. The amperometric titration curves provide well defined breaks at the point where the molecular ratio of UO_2^{2+} : $\text{As}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ is 1 : 1, confirming the formation of $\text{UO}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{As}_2\text{O}_3$ in the pH range 5.0—6.8 according to the equation :

All the amperometric titration curves are regular in form. It takes a little time for the current values to become steady and thorough stirring in the vicinity of end points has a favourable effect. Presence of ethanol slightly improves the end points as it decreases the solubility of the compounds formed and minimises hydrolysis and absorption effects. In view of the accuracy and reproducibility of the titrations, they may be successfully employed for the quantitative determination of UO_2^{2+} ions in solutions at suitable concentrations and pH ranges.

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